

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
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Horizon scanning workshop – Outline/Flow chart

General meeting

COHESIVE

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Date	27 November, Time: 13:40-18:10
Venue	Rome (ISS)
Meeting	COHESIVE general meeting
Room	

Background

Various organizations have addressed that foresight studies regarding one health is of interest. However, looking into the future and foresight studies are complex. There are many options for futures, but it generally involves identifying areas of uncertainty, challenges, underlying drivers and opportunities. In other words, futures are about a structured manner to explore possible and preferable futures. Foresight is a process to conduct futures work and horizon scanning is a specific technique and various horizon scanning tools are available (UK GOV, 2018). There are also various terms and definitions and one that will be used for this workshop is following:

“Horizon scanning is a specific foresight methodology that utilizes various steps to identify issues at the edge of current thinking that may have significant impact in the medium to long term future” (FAO, 2014).

Aim:

The aim of this workshop is to conduct a horizon scanning pilot exercise to identify “drivers of change” in order to strengthen European one health.

*One Health EJP
General meeting COHESIVE hosted by ISS*

Pilot Horizon scanning exercise flow chart:

In order to have an efficient workshop following the below outline will serve as a base. Some criteria for making the work are that there is a network with expert that all can contribute with various one health issues that is of relevance for the next years. The COHESIVE workshop on the 27th of November will follow the procedure. The workshop will be highlighted to generate a long and a short, revised list.

The above figure is from the article Wintle et al 2017 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.30247>). It outlines the seven stages of the horizon scanning procedure (Sutherland et al. 2011) used to identify emerging biological engineering (DOI:10.1111/j.210X.2010.00083).

Based on the above horizon scanning tool following 20 emerging issues in biological engineering were outlined:

Issues most relevant in the near term (< 5 years)

- Artificial photosynthesis and carbon capture for producing biofuels
- Enhanced photosynthesis for agricultural productivity
- New approaches to synthetic gene drives
- Human genome editing
- Accelerating defense agency research in biological engineering

Issues most relevant in the intermediate term (5-10 years)

- Regenerative medicine: 3D printing body parts and tissue engineering
- Microbiome-based therapies
- Producing vaccines and human therapies in plants
- Manufacturing illegal drugs using engineered organisms

- Reassigning codons as genetic firewalls
- Rise of automated tools for biological design, test and optimisation
- Biology as an information science: Impacts on global governance
- Intersection of information security and bio-automation
- Effects of the Nagoya protocol on biological engineering
- Corporate espionage and biocrime

Issues most relevant in the longer term (>10 years)

- New makers disrupt pharmaceutical markets
- Platform technologies to address emerging disease pandemics
- Challenges to taxonomy-based descriptions and management of biological risk
- Shifting ownership models in biotechnology
- Securing the critical infrastructure needed to deliver the bioeconomy

Workflow:

Information security: It is only public, open and unclassified data that is considered.

Activities prior the meeting

Individually based activity.

Look for interesting topics concerning one health issues. It can be issues found in newspapers, social media, reports, conferences or publications.

Activities on the COHESIVE workshop

Each workshop participant shall present 2-5 one health issues. After presenting the issues a “Long list” will be generated. Based on the long list a short list will be assessed. Group discussion will take place to discuss and revise the list.

References

FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations), Italy (2014). Horizon Scanning and Foresight – An overview of approaches and possible applications in Food Safety. Background paper 2: FAO Early Warning/Rapid Alert and Horizon Scanning Food Safety Technical Workshop, Rome, Italy.

Sutherland, W.J., Fleishman, E., Macia, M.B., Pretty, J., Rudd, M.A., (2011) Methods for collaboratively identifying research priorities and emerging issues in science and policy. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* (2), 238-247. (DOI:10.1111/j.210X.2010.00083.).

Wintle, B.C. et al. (2017). A transatlantic perspective on 20 emerging issues in biological engineering. *eLife* (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.30247>).

UK GOV (United Kingdom Government Blog), (2018). The Future Toolkit – Tools for Future Thinking and Foresight Across UK Government, Government Office for Science.
<https://foresightprojects.blog.gov.uk/2018/11/01/futures-foresight-and-horizon-scanning-finding-a-way-forward/>

Appendix 1: Agenda COHESIVE general workshop in Rome at ISS.

Day	Time	WP2.1/2.3	WP2.2	WP3.1	WP3.2	WP3.3	WP4.1	WP4.2	WP4.3
Wednesday November 27	8.30-9.00	Registration							
	9.00-9.40	Plenary session discussing WP2							
	9.40-10.20	Plenary session discussing WP3							
	10.20-10.50	Coffee/tea break							
	10.50-11.30	Plenary session discussion WP4							
	11.30-12.10	Plenary session discussion WP4							
	12.10-12.40	Tripartite zoonoses guide by FAO (to be confirmed)							
	12.40-13.40	Lunch							
	13.40-14.30				workshop 'Horizon scanning'				
	14.30-15.40	Coffee/tea break							
	15.40-16.10	Coffee/tea break							
	16.10-17.00				ONLY ON INVITATION				
	17.00-18.10	Optional: Diner together							
evening	Optional: Diner together								

Thursday November 28	9.00-9.45								
	9.45-10.30								
	10.30-11.00	Coffee/tea break							
	11.00-11.45								
	11.45-12.30								
	12.30-13.30	Lunch							
	13.30-14.15	Fill in depending on the needs during the meeting. Certainly a session on WP3.2 and WP4.4							
	14.15-15.00								
	15.00-15.30	Coffee/tea break							
	15.30-16.30	Fill in depending on the needs during the meeting							
	16.30-17.15	WP2/WP3/WP4 Plenary discussion & general items							
	17.00-18.00	WP2/WP3/WP4 Plenary discussion & general items							
	evening	Optional: Diner together							

Friday November 29	9.00-9.45								
	9.45-10.30								
	10.30-11.00	Coffee/tea break							
	11.00-11.45								
	11.45-12.30								
	12.30-13.30	Lunch							
	13.30-14.30	Planning, wrap up & closure							

= planned meetings